

Why God Does Not Answer Our Prayers?

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The rapid outbreak of coronavirus - novel COVID-19 pandemic across the globe caught the world unprepared, ill-equipped and untrained. Our world, with its leading scientists hasn't yet found any medicine for cure or vaccine. COVID-19 has, therefore, made thousands and thousands across the world to breathe their last. It has left millions of people either on ventilators or in isolation or home-quarantine. COVID-19 attacked and attacks the people who are either weak with their immune system or weak with their hearts or weak with their sugar and sodium levels. It appears that COVID-19 attacks the weaker side of the people, as human beings generally do. Even satanic or evil spirit loads its gun on the shoulder of the people who are weak, imprudent and impolite and then encourage them to attack one another or attack the Creator of their life, love, faith and hope or attack their own or other organizations illogically. People, who are strong with their spiritual, emotional and physical immune system, can easily resist or can combat with COVID-19 and bounce back to life as testimonies of experiences of love, faith and hope.

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Where is Our God?

Having trapped the world unprepared and ill-equipped, COVID-19 has started behaving as an almost unstoppable phenomenon. It created ripples of terror, fear, anxieties, uncertainties among people. One thing, COVID-19 remained absolutely impartial, unbiased and unprejudiced. No nation, no race, no religion, no political party, no one whether rich or poor, educated or illiterate could influence COVID-19 and could stop it infecting the others. It created fear of death among the people. The complete lockdown restricted the movements of the people to their homes and houses. Lockdown perhaps led people to introspect their independence, making them more insecure about life; that is, death can come at any time.

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The rise in the number of deaths in the world confirmed the insecurity of life due to COVID-19. Panic among the people grew. People, according to their personalities, nationalities, religions, experiences, portfolios, etc., started reacting and explaining the COVID-19 pandemic. Responses from politicians, business people, government, philanthropists, religious leaders, faithful, doctors, health workers, employers, employees, administrations, poor, migrants etc. were so varied from one another and were yet mixed. Their reactions were revolving around the fear of death, insecurity, helplessness and hopelessness. People encountering helplessness but having faith in God perhaps began asking questions: Where is God? Is

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COVID-19 pandemic greater than God? Why is He not answering our prayers? Has He stopped loving and caring for His people?

Walking Before the Lord with Faith, Hope and Love

Questions about God, He alone can answer them and in His own time. He has the absolute right and freedom to answer our prayers. Finite beings like us will not be able to fathom the mind and the heart of God. At the same time, there is hope. Scripture bears enough evidence for our hope. The biblical personalities confidently profess that God answers our prayers. They too like us underwent the pangs of uncertainty, fears of death, insecurity, helplessness and often hopelessness. These feelings were accompanied by the noncooperation and noncollaboration of the disappointed, discouraged and frustrated people of God. Yet, God was faithful. God was there as a pillar of cloud during the day and pillar of fire during the night. Thus, the prophets and the leaders encouraged the people of God not to succumb to discouragement and despair but always walk before the Lord with faith, hope and love.

In these trying days of COVID-19 pandemic, similar scenes are played out. We observe people filled with fear, anxiety, insecurity, helplessness and despair on one side, and the others, who often boldly do not cooperate and collaborate with the invoked and necessary safety dynamics. Lack of planning is seen on the part of the authorities not being sensitive to the plight of the poor, migrants, and disorganized labour force. They had nowhere to go for help to meet their essential needs. Essential commodities too, were not made available at the right time. Cooperation and collaboration are effective means to help one another combat the spread and effects of

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covid-19 and therefore, government agencies, church authorities even Pope Francis is encouraging people to participate in the march towards ending the pandemic. In our cooperation and collaboration with all the humans, we might be able to stand as a live witness to the faith, hope and love God has planted in us through Jesus.

Not My Will, but Thy Will

There might be other questions as to why such pandemic and why God cannot stop it? Is there a plan of God behind this pandemic? These questions also need to be addressed. Perhaps Jesus, as he was in the garden of Gethsemane, asked the same question to his Father. Why should I undergo this suffering? If it is Thy will, please take away this cup. But it is not my will, but Thy will be done. He surrendered his total self in the hands of the Father and resolutely walked through his passion and death. He showed in his life, passion and death that love has the power to conquer all evil, including death. Perhaps, here is an invitation for us to ponder on such a powerful message and allow our lives to be rooted and grounded in love and show such love in action. If we do so, then we will be participating in the passion, death and resurrection of the Lord. May the mysteries of the life of Christ: passion, death and resurrection strengthen our hope in God and one another! As the fruit of our prayers, our hope in God and one another can build better humanity according to the will of God, that is, love your God with your soul, mind and heart; love your neighbour as you love yourself, and love your enemies. May these COVID-19 pandemic experiences, both positive and negative, reinforce our hope - hope that builds harmonious humanity!